

Towards multifunctional agricultural landscapes in Europe: Assessing and governing synergies between food production, biodiversity, and ecosystem services – TALE

Policy options to best reconcile food production, biodiversity and ecosystem service provision

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1. Introduction / Background / Executive Summary

The overall aim of the TALE project was to find land use strategies that enhance both biodiversity and ecosystem services in agricultural landscapes. It aimed to identify synergies and minimize trade-offs among biodiversity and ecosystem services and to analyse policy instruments that could help to manage those synergies and trade-offs.

Therefore, a set of different models was developed and applied in work package 2 of the project (WP2) to assess the effect of management practices according to policies that refer to two extreme land use strategies: land sharing and land sparing (for the debate on the two strategies, cf. Phalan et al., 2011; von Wehrden et al., 2014). Each case-study developed stakeholder-based scenarios (WP3) for a land sharing, a land sparing and a balanced (or business as usual) situation, projected for the year 2030. The model evaluation of those scenarios revealed first insights into the effects of different land use strategies on selected indicators for biodiversity and a set of ecosystem services, and possible synergies and trade-offs among them. However, to best reconcile food production, biodiversity and ecosystem service provision, one has to go beyond scenario analysis and use explorative modelling approaches to move from black-and-white choices towards more nuanced, context-specific solutions (Butsic and Kuemmerle, 2015; Seppelt et al., 2013). This can be achieved by coupling simulation models with metaheuristics, such as evolutionary algorithms, to explore a large number of land use/land management configurations and to identify those solutions that are close to Pareto-optimality (e.g. Memmah et al., 2015). For Pareto-optimal solutions no objective can be further improved without worsening another. They hence illustrate the best possible trade-offs among conflicting objectives. From such a set of best alternatives, decision makers can discuss and select appropriate solutions according to their preferences (Cord et al., 2017). Within WP4 of the TALE project, Kaim et al. (2018) reviewed multi-criteria optimization techniques for agricultural land use allocation and their use to support decision making.

To identify Pareto-optimal solutions in the TALE project, WP4 developed the land use optimization software CoMOLA (Strauch and Pätzold, 2018) which can be used to optimize the allocation of land use or land management practices for multiple objectives while considering basic land use transition and composition constraints. As the framework allows users to integrate any kind of simulation models, e.g. process-based or statistical or both at the same time, it is considered as a useful tool for a broad range of spatial allocation studies. Due to time constraints, CoMOLA was only applied in the Dutch and the German case study. This report summarizes the outcomes of both optimization studies with respect to land use strategies and policy options to best reconcile food production, biodiversity and ecosystem service provision. As a further example, policy recommendations for the Austrian case study are given based on scenario analyses.

We found that all environmental objectives (biodiversity and ecosystem service indicators) can be improved simultaneously - with minimal losses in agricultural production, when measures supported by the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) are spatially targeted.

2. Optimization case studies

2.1 Kromme Rijn area

The optimization case study for the Kromme Rijn area was published by Verhagen et al. (2018). In the following, we will give a brief summary with a stronger focus on policy implications.

Study area

The Kromme Rijn area (Fig. 1) is a peri-urban agriculturally dominated landscape of ~219 km², located in the Province of Utrecht, The Netherlands. The landscape is characterized by an old tributary of the river Rhine, the Kromme Rijn, meandering through the area. The agricultural landscape in the area is rich in woody linear elements and characterized by a NW-SE gradient in openness. In the northern section, the banks of the Kromme Rijn are flanked by estates dating back to the 19th century. Pasture production around these estates is intertwined with remnants of natural vegetation and bordered in the north by forests. In the rest of the area the main agricultural activity is dairy farming combined with fruit production on sandy and clay levee deposits of the former riverbed. In addition to its agricultural function, the area has high aesthetic quality and is an important recreational area for the city of Utrecht.

Fig. 1: Land use/land management map of the Kromme Rijn area depicting the main agricultural land systems. The inset of the map shows the location of the study area (in red) within The Netherlands. The land system map is depicted with a 2 km buffer. Source: Verhagen et al. (2018).

Objectives and management options

In the Dutch case study, we aimed at optimizing the following objectives:

- Fruit yield production from orchards (maximize)
- Aesthetic quality (maximize)
- Great crested newt (*Triturus cristatus*) habitat (maximize)
- Pasture production for dairy cows (minimize loss from potential maximum production)

The underlying models for each objective were written in R (R Core Team, 2016) and explained in Verhagen et al. (2018). For the optimization, we allowed management changes on a total of 418 patches (277 pasture farms and 141 fruit orchards). Each of those patches can be managed either conventionally or organically and can include linear elements or not; these measures represent on-farm and thus land sharing strategies. Moreover, pasture can be taken out of production as an off-farm or land sparing strategy. Both on- and off-farm measures are supported by the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). We ran a total of three optimization experiments, considering 1) only on-farm measures, 2) only the off-farm measure and 3) all options, by combining on-farm and off-farm measures. Each experiment was constraint by both transition rules, defining which category of land use / land management can change into which other, and the possible minimum and maximum extent of those changes. Further details are provided in Verhagen et al. (2018).

Results and policy implications

The optimization has revealed that all measures (on-farm, off-farm, and combined) could improve all objectives simultaneously. However, the improvement of each object differed between on- and off-farm measures (Verhagen et al., 2018).

The solely focus on on-farm measures strongly enhanced fruit yield, but had a smaller positive impact on newt habitat; while focusing on off-farm measures had a strong positive impact on newt habitat, but hardly enhanced fruit yield. By combining on- and off-farm measures (all options experiment), it was possible to achieve high levels of both newt habitat and fruit yield. In general, increases in newt habitat and landscape aesthetics could only be achieved with decreasing pasture production and thus always resulted in a trade-off. In contrast, high fruit yields can also be achieved without losses in pasture production, due to on-farm measures on orchards.

Figure 2 shows the achieved (Pareto-optimal) solutions for the all-options experiment. Compared to the current situation, multiple solutions performed better for all objectives. Taking an example solution, it might be possible to increase newt habitat (+22%), reduce pasture production loss (+22%) and simultaneously increase the other environmental objectives. In contrast, the nature conservation plan (NBP in Fig. 2) developed by the province to enhance species conservation for the Kromme Rjin area (Utrecht Province, 2017) would result in a 15.5% increase of newt habitat, at the cost of strongly decreasing fruit and pasture yields (-19.4% and -37.2%, respectively). The nature conservation plan, which addresses more species beyond the newt, is a regional policy that promotes both off-farm (agricultural land taken out of production) and on-farm measures (in particular the establishment of green linear elements, such as hedges and tree lines on agricultural land). Our results indicate that with different allocation schemes of the same measures we can

achieve even more newt habitat but at the same time also substantially higher values in all other objectives.

Fig. 2: The set of Pareto-optimal solutions for the “all options” experiment relative to the current landscape (C). NBP refers to the nature conservation plan. Compared to C and NBP, the whole set of Pareto solutions scores better in terms of aesthetics (lower central panel) and orchard production (lower right panel). Therefore, in the top and lower left panel, all solutions to the upper right of C or NBP score better on all objectives compared to the current landscape or the nature conservation plan, respectively. Source: Verhagen et al. (2018).

Figure 3 provides frequency maps of on- and off-farm measures based on the all-option experiment. Only a few areas were assigned a measure across most or all Pareto-optimal allocation schemes (class 95-100% in Fig. 3A). These areas were mainly located in and around orchards in the centre of the Kromme Rijn. This showed a mismatch with the areas designated in the nature conservation plan, as these are mostly at the edge of the Kromme Rijn area, for example around rivers and existing nature areas (Fig. 3D). The conservation plan is solely developed for species protection, but does address more species than just the newt, partly explaining the difference in locations. Our results indicate that if additional objectives and agri-environment measures would be included in the conservation plan, the preferred locations for these measures would be located differently. Mainly, preferred

locations would move to the centre of the Kromme Rijn area in and around orchards. The frequency with which a cell is assigned to a measure does not indicate the type assigned to that cell. Therefore we separately identified the frequency of on-farm (Fig. 3B) and off-farm measures per cell (Fig. 3C). Specific locations have a high frequency of on-farm measures, especially in and around orchards. The frequency for off-farm measures per location was far lower (Fig. 3C) indicating that no location has a clear priority to be taken out of production. Thus, although a combination of both on- and off-farm measures is preferred, only priority locations for on-farm measures could be identified.

Fig. 3: Priority maps for agri-environment measures in the Kromme Rijn area. The higher the priority the more often a field is assigned to an agri-environment measure. Results are depicted for all options, i.e. a combination of both on-farm and off-farm measures. The maps depict priorities for (A) conventional versus all other agri-environment measures, (B) on-farm measures versus all other, (C) off-farm measures versus all other and (D) the areas targeted in the nature conservation plan to be taken out of production (blue areas in D). Source: Verhagen et al. (2018).

As a result, we found that all considered agri-environment measures could improve all environmental objectives simultaneously, but that the improvement of each objective differed between on- and off-farm measures. Either choosing a management strategy focused on “off farm” or “on farm” resulted in a strong trade-off between new habitat and fruit yield. Allowing a mixture of measures could alleviate this trade-off. This provides important information for landscape planners, as it does not only show that trade-offs exist, but more importantly, it shows how these trade-offs can be effectively navigated through relevant agri-environment measures.

Our models for fruit yield, aesthetics and newt habitat were sensitive to landscape configuration including functions related to surrounding landscape (distance decay), edge effects and linear elements. The importance of landscape configuration for ecosystem services has been previously addressed using a conceptual model (Mitchell et al., 2015) or model comparisons (Lautenbach et al., 2011; Verhagen et al., 2016). The Pareto-frontier in our optimization analysis can be interpreted as the set of optimal landscape configurations for increasing opportunity costs. It highlights what can be optimally achieved when combining the effect of the area of interventions (composition) with the spatial allocation (configuration). In addition, our results highlight the importance of linear elements in agricultural landscapes for ecosystem service supply. Increases in newt habitat suitability and aesthetic quality of the on-farm experiment can be solely attributed to increasing the amount of linear elements given that organic farming has no impact on these objectives in our models. Previous research linked these elements to a diverse set of ecosystem services and argued for the inclusion of elements in landscape optimization approaches (Jones et al., 2013; Verhagen et al., 2016). To our knowledge this is the first application of linear elements in landscape optimization. More importantly, we demonstrated that a landscape optimization without these elements would result in a less optimal outcome (not shown here, see Fig. 2 in Verhagen et al., 2018), thus providing evidence for the importance of accounting for configuration and linear elements in landscape planning.

The current nature conservation plan focuses on taking designated areas out of production to meet species conservation objectives. Here we showed that with a more optimal allocation of measures, it was possible to meet species conservation objectives while simultaneously improving on a number of other environmental objectives. Moreover, we showed that the addition of on-farm measures in combination with off-farm measures (thus a mixture of land sharing of land sparing strategies) is more effective in realising the objectives. The nature conservation plan combines taking designated areas out of production with promoting voluntary measures on agricultural land. We showed that explicitly incorporating on-farm measures could be a more effective strategy. Focusing on establishment of linear elements and organic management might be more easily implemented because it involves lower costs to farmers, as well as the possibility to obtain financial support for establishing linear elements.

In addition, our spatial analyses showed that priority areas for agri-environment measures do not align with currently designated areas. These results can assist spatial planners in designing future plans. The current management strategy focuses on farms forming voluntary collectives proposing to implement agri-environment measures. Spatially explicit knowledge on the location of priority locations for restoration can help evaluate the effectiveness of these proposals.

2.2 Lossa basin

Study area

The Lossa basin (Fig. 4) is a rural, agriculturally dominated area of 141 km², located in Central Germany. Ranging from 97 to 240 m in elevation, it is a rather flat lowland area with a few porphy hills in the central and eastern parts. The basin drains into the Lossa River, a small tributary of the Mulde River. Large parts of the river system can run dry during longer

dry spells in summer. The landscape is characterized by intensive farming on fertile loess soils, mainly for producing winter wheat, rapeseed, winter barley and corn on large fields bounded by hedges and tree rows. Urban areas, grasslands (often also intensively used) and small forests prevail along the stream network, whereas larger forests dominate on steeper slopes (porphyr hills) and on sandy soils in the Northeast (Dahlener Heide). The area hosts many species and natural habitat types protected by European law, among them different open-land bird species.

Fig. 4: Land use/land management map for the Lossa river basin (Germany). Source: ATKIS Basis-DLM (Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy, year 2010), refined for the types of grassland using the CIR biotope and land use mapping (Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology, year 2005) and refined for the types of forest using CORINE Land Cover data (European Environment Agency, year 2012).

Objectives and management options

In German case study, we aimed at optimizing the following objectives:

- Agricultural production (maximize)
- Open-land bird species habitat (maximize)
- Nitrate-N load in the Lossa River (minimize)
- Low-flow of the Lossa River (maximize)

Low-flow (as 5th percentile of daily stream flows in $\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$) and Nitrate-N loads (kg N yr^{-1}) were estimated using the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT, Arnold et al., 2012),

agricultural production (as basin-wide gross margin in € yr⁻¹) was calculated based on SWAT simulated crop yields combined with crop-specific market prices and production costs, whereas open-land bird habitat (% change compared to the current habitat area) was estimated using nine different RandomForest models, one for each of the nine observed bird species breeding in agricultural sites of the Lossa basin (Strauch et al., 2018).

Our optimization experiment was directly based on the scenarios for land sharing, land sparing and business-as-usual as developed together with stakeholders from different sectors for the Middle Mulde basin (WP3). However, to keep the complexity of the optimization problem within reasonable limits, we only focused on the Lossa basin and thus on a smaller part of the Middle Mulde basin (cf. Fig. 4). The scenarios differed in terms of both spatially explicit changes of land use/land cover and general changes in land management. The business as usual scenario assumed a continuation of current trends until 2030, i.e. increasing built-up (+3.34% of total basin area) and forested area (+0.55%) at the cost of cropland. In land sharing, we also assumed a conversion of cropland to forest (+0.61%) and built-up area (+1.12%). Here, the increase of built-up area was smaller according to the political target of the Federal state of Saxony to reduce urbanization (in hectare per day) from currently six to two. Moreover, all intensively used grasslands (8.5% of the basin area) were assumed to be extensively used. In contrast, the land sparing scenario assumed no increase of built-up area at all but an increase of cropland (+1.51%) and forest (+0.24%) at the cost of grasslands. The exact locations of those changes are provided in the study of Strauch et al. (2018). Moreover, we considered general changes in land management as presented in Table 1, assuming extensification for land sharing and intensification in case of land sparing.

Tab. 1: General land management changes in each of the different scenarios, summarized for the total basin area.

	Current	Business as usual	Land sharing	Land sparing
Crop rotations	According to crop statistics	Slightly less diverse	Slightly more diverse	Strongly less diverse
Organic farming (%)	4	5	20	0
Fertilizer (kg N/P ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	112/31	105/36	81/30	122/39
Tillage (% conserv. till.)	60	70	100	60
Linear landscape elements (% on HRU* area), including filter strips in land sharing	According to land use map (Fig. 4)	No change	Increase to upper quartile of current if below	Decrease to median of current if above

*HRU = Hydrologic Response Unit, the smallest spatial unit in SWAT, representing a unique combination of land use and soil in a certain subbasin.

While a land sparing situation is assumed to be driven by more market liberal agricultural policies, our land sharing scenario relates to instruments of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), such as payments for organic farming and agri-environment-climate measures (AECM) supporting filter strips, linear elements, conservation tillage as well as extensive management of grassland (e.g. less fertilizer and harvests) and cropland (e.g. including legumes in the crop rotation).

For land sharing, our models predicted strong increases in bird habitat (+19.6% compared to current) and water quality (7.5% reduction of Nitrate-N load). However, this came at the cost of substantially decreasing agricultural gross margins (-48.9%), while lowflow was reduced by 7.7%. In contrast, the land sparing scenario was evaluated best for agricultural production (loss of only 4.2% compared to current) but performed poor in terms of Nitrate-N loads (increase of 28.3%), while slightly increasing bird habitat (+5.6%) and reducing lowflow (-3.8%). The business as usual scenario resulted into intermediate changes, in-between land sharing and land sparing, except for low-flow (no change) (cf. Strauch et al., 2018).

As a result, the scenarios indicated strong trade-offs between agricultural production and both bird habitat and water quality. By using CoMOLA, we aimed to minimize these trade-offs. In particular, we wanted to investigate if multifunctionality can be increased by a spatial targeting of the different scenario options at the level of HRUs (Hydrologic Response Units). HRUs are the smallest spatial units of the SWAT model, representing a unique combination of land use and soil in a certain subbasin. HRUs can hence vary in size. Within the optimization, each of the HRUs larger than five hectare ($n=185$) could be assigned the land use and land management information of either the current situation, the business as usual, the land sharing or the land sparing scenario.

Results and policy implications

The optimization experiment revealed how the different objectives would relate to each other when optimally allocating the different scenario land use/land management options at the level of HRUs. Agricultural production shows a trade-off to all other environmental objectives. The trade-off is very strong and almost linear with water quality (Pearson's $r = -0.96$), less strong but still remarkable with bird habitat ($r = -0.69$) and rather weak with low-flow ($r = -0.20$). The trade-offs of agricultural production with both bird habitat and low-flow show a convex form, indicating that both objectives can be maximised at moderate agricultural production levels. Vice versa, all three environmental objectives are positively correlated and thus show synergistic relationships. For bird habitat, we found relatively strong synergies with water quality ($r = 0.63$) and low-flow ($r = 0.50$), while water quality and low-flow are less correlated ($r=0.22$).

The benefit of explorative modelling using multi-objective optimization over a simple scenario analysis is shown in Fig. 6. All stakeholder-based scenarios (business as usual, land sharing and land sparing) can be dominated in multiple objectives at the same time. As an example, a smart scenario combination might outperform each of the single scenarios in terms of bird habitat (+25.4% compared to current), water quality (-10.2% Nitrate load) and low-flow (+2.7%), with a relatively small loss in agricultural production (-13.3%). This solution ("best

compromise” Fig. 6) might be preferable if all objectives are weighted equally, as it provides the maximum sum of all objectives when they are normalized to a range between 0 and 1.

While each of the three stakeholder scenarios can be clearly dominated in one or more objective(s) without worsening at least one other objective, this is not true for the current situation. The current situation is already close the possible maximum value in agricultural production. Further increasing agricultural production would involve decreasing water quality or low-flow. This means, the current situation itself can be seen as a Pareto-optimal solution.

Fig. 5: Correlation (Pearson's r) matrix among the objectives considering all Pareto-optimal solutions (n = 2419). With p-values < 0.001 (indicated by *) all results are highly significant. The four-dimensional objective space is displayed in scatterplots for each combination of two objectives. Water quality is defined as Nitrate-N load multiplied with -1.**

Thus, in order to enhance all environmental objectives in the Lossa basin, one has to accept losses in agricultural production. However, as shown for the best compromise solution, remarkable environmental enhancements can be achieved at relatively low opportunity costs. Policy options to best reconcile food production, biodiversity and ecosystem service provision might therefore support such a solution.

Fig. 6: The set of Pareto-optimal solutions (spatial scenario combinations) in the objective space compared to the current situation and the “pure” scenarios for business as usual, land sharing, and land sparing. The figure also depicts best solutions for single objectives and a compromise solution which provides the maximum sum of all objectives (each normalized to range between 0 and 1).

Fig. 7 illustrates the spatial combination of single land use strategies (scenarios) in order to achieve the best compromise solution. According to that, only a smaller part of the Lossa basin (27.5%) should be managed more extensively as defined by the land sharing scenario (less fertilizer application, more linear elements, etc., see Tab. 1). This type of management should be implemented in the south-eastern part of the basin, where landscape heterogeneity is currently highest. Landscape heterogeneity, as a mixture of different land covers in close distance to smaller tributary streams of the Lossa River and even urban areas, is favoured by many open-land bird species. Extensification in those areas might therefore efficiently increase the suitable bird habitat (as confirmed by the map for maximum bird habitat, Fig. 7). Land sparing was suggested for only 13.3% of the total area, preferably on smaller HRUs in the central and western parts. Here, the land sparing scenario included small sites for afforestation (Strauch et al., 2018) which might again favour bird habitat.

However, land sparing also included intensified agricultural management (e.g. more fertilizer) and the central and western part of the basin seems most suitable to efficiently increase agricultural gross margins (cf. map for maximum production in Fig. 7). For 25.7% of the area, the business as usual scenario was suggested. The allocation of this scenario (which foresees the strongest expansion of urban areas) on sites surrounding the main stream of the Lossa River seemed in particular efficient to increase lowflow. However, since we did not account for increased water use along with urbanisation in our hydrological model, this might be a model artefact. For the rest of the area (33.5%), the current management (i.e. no change at all) was suggested. Together with land sparing, the current management was important to keep agricultural production on a high level.

Fig. 7: Best solutions for single objectives and a compromise solution (“mid-range”) shown as land use/land management maps. The bars show the percentage of each scenario on the total optimization area.

As a result, the optimization revealed that all environmental objectives in the Lossa basin can be enhanced at relatively low opportunity costs. Spatial targeting of measures is thus a key factor for efficiently enhancing multifunctionality. According to our results, spatial targeting can only minimize the loss in agricultural production. A full compensation of losses might, however, be possible by agri-environmental payments supporting extensification and the implementation of filter strips and linear elements (e.g. CAP instruments), for which the economic impact was not taken into account in our model simulations.

3. Reports from other TALE case studies based on scenario analysis

The Austrian case study in the Mostviertel region analyzed three contrasting stakeholder-based land use scenarios in a quantitative integrated modelling framework including the biophysical process model EPIC (Williams et al., 1989), the regional land use optimization model PASMA[grid] (Kirchner et al., 2016), and several indicator frameworks to estimate ecosystem services. The stakeholder-based land use scenarios depict a situation dominated by land sharing, land sparing and a balanced situation between land sharing and sparing for observed climate conditions and are compared to current land use.

Aggregated results are presented in Fig. 8 for selected ecosystem services and biodiversity indicators. The balanced scenario can be considered as business as usual scenario. It is similar to the current land use with changing indicators mainly resulting from loss of agricultural land to urban areas. Land sharing shows declines in agricultural production from extensification, which positively affects several indicators such as excess nitrogen or soil erosion on cropland. However, the best indicator values for biodiversity can be achieved with land sparing according to the results. Particularly for land sparing, the indicator results have been contested by the regional stakeholders. They argued that high landscape aesthetics from such a scenario may only occur in the first years if set-aside land is colorful and diverse with respect to plant species. In the long run, any unmanaged site will follow succession by shrubs and trees eventually losing its attractiveness and ecological value according to the stakeholders.

Fig. 8: Ecosystem services and biodiversity indicators for four land use scenarios in the Austrian Mostviertel case study (LSH = land sharing, LSP = land sparing, BAL = balanced, REF = current land use, all assuming observed climate (past). Values are compared to REF (100%).

The scenarios show a reasonable range of future land use states with diverse outcomes for ecosystem services and biodiversity. They may not be Pareto-optimal choices because changes in land use may eventually improve some indicators while keeping others unaffected at this aggregate level. However, assuming that scenarios are representative and given the legitimization by the stakeholder process, subsequent steps are the evaluation of

each of the scenarios with respect to the societal preferences for the bundle of services and finally policy instruments to achieve these states.

Regional stakeholders showed a clear preference for the balanced scenario, some sympathy for land sharing but strongly rejected land sparing. Reasons for the latter include the feared risk of declining landscape aesthetics, the expected loss of biodiversity, and the further intensification of production in some parts of the region. Stakeholders' preference for current land use can be interpreted as choice between the trade-offs of further landscape and biodiversity improvements resulting from the land sharing scenario and the maintenance of the regional provisioning services according to the balanced scenario. Nevertheless, stakeholders observe declining ecosystem services and biodiversity from past and current land use changes, which are heading towards a land sparing scenario.

To maintain current land use and to prevent developments towards land sparing, which would result from market liberal agricultural policies, governance instruments are required. Stakeholders highlighted the need for maintaining CAP instruments such as direct payments and second pillar payments on rural development. They consider large parts of their region as disfavored with respect to natural and farm structural production conditions and conclude that farms in these parts would not be able to compete on global markets under a market liberal political framework. Agri-environmental payments for extensive production such as organic farming and less-favored area payments to maintain agricultural land use particularly on steep slopes are required to halt intensification pressures, loss of landscape elements such as iconic orchard trees, and land abandonment. However, stakeholders also see a role for improving education of farmers and raising awareness of ecosystem services and benefits resulting from biodiversity maintenance.

4. Conclusions and outlook

In both optimization case studies, in the Kromme Rijn area and in the Lossa basin, we have shown the potential of reconciling agricultural production, ecosystem services and biodiversity. In both cases, a combination of different options referring to either land sharing or land sparing was evaluated best, pointing out the need for nuanced context-specific solutions. In the Kromme Rijn area, best solutions can be achieved by applying both on- and off-farm measures, whereas the on-farm measures (organic management and linear elements) should be allocated in and around orchards. In the Lossa basin, on-farm measures of extensification (land sharing strategy) might be most effective in more heterogeneous areas in the south-eastern part, while a few areas should be managed more intensively to keep the productivity of the basin on a high level. In conclusion, we found that measures supported by the CAP can be fully effective when spatially targeted. The need for maintaining CAP instruments, such as direct payments and second pillar payments on rural development, was also highlighted by the Austrian case study.

In the next step, the optimization results of the German case study need to be analyzed in more detail, e.g. by a spatial factor analysis relating single measures to landscape characteristics (such as soil, topography, distance to forest edges, streams, etc.), to gain a better understanding of why those spatial management patterns emerged. We will work on methods to better visualize and navigate through the objective space of Pareto-optimal solutions. We will also continue the work with the German stakeholder group to identify and discuss best solutions according to their preferences.

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